

Contribution of Mining and Industrial Activities to Air Pollution in Zambia: A Review

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Abstract

This review focuses on evidence of impact of mining and industrial activities on air quality in Zambia. For about 120 years, sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and particulate matter (PM) released from the Copperbelt's copper mines have been the main sources of air pollution in Zambia, with legal immunity conferred to polluters in earlier years. Mining companies have remained reluctant, and are continuing to resist calls to comply with emission limits; audits reveal unacceptable levels of non-compliance. The dawn of mining diversification and the country's economy has brought forth cement, lime manufacturing, manganese processing, thermal power generation and steel manufacturing with concomitant emissions of metals, NO_x, CO and Black carbon to air. Impacts on human health, mostly attributable to cardiorespiratory causes. Damaged ecosystems, acidification of soils, losses of biological species and toxic metals bioaccumulating on the food chain, advanced corrosion and damage to structures overtime are some of the environmental impacts. Pollution from the lead and manganese mines in Kabwe and Serenje, respectively, constitute acute pollution disasters. Though the country has a workable legal framework (Environmental Management Act), this is marred by lack of compliance and enforcement. We conclude that Zambia must invest in properly reading its air, actualizing compliance and enforcement, investing in clean technology, monitoring air quality, targeting front line health gestion, and solid waste management.

Keywords: *Air Pollution, Mining Emissions, Industrial Emissions,, Air Pollution Impacts.*

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Introduction

Industrialization is a primary factor in economic development in every part of the world, and nations place considerable emphasis on its

development. This is because they play an important role as contributors to gross domestic product (GDP), employment and innovation. The mining industry has largely influenced the economy of Zambia for more than 90 years

when the first commercial mine was opened early in the 20th century. For a period of over 80 years, copper production has been the major stimulant for all economic activity, fishing mining as the pillar of the national economy. This reliance is clearly illustrated by the contribution that the sector makes, as much as 17.4 percent of the country's GDP in 2024 (Aurélien et al., 2022; Kolala & Dokowe, 2021; MoF, 2024; Simutanyi, 2008). Despite this predominance the manufacturing sector is assuming a more and more important place, the contribution to the national GDP of Zambia's manufacturing industries has been 9.3 percent in 2024 (MoF, 2024).

Zambia's mineral riches extend far beyond the well-known copper, comprising a variety of products including cobalt, gold, nickel, lead, and precious stones. These minerals are widely distributed, but have been concentrated geographically in the Copperbelt and North-Western Provinces until recently. Data for 2024, however, indicate a marked change in this respect since the Central Province has sanctioned more projects by the Zambia Environmental Management Agency (ZEMA) than have Lusaka and the Copperbelt. This trend is primarily due to rapid growth in mining activity in the Mkushi and Serenje Districts of the Central Province (ZEMA, 2024).

For many decades, however, copper mining operations in the Copperbelt have suffered from poor environmental management, whether they have been in private or public ownership. A legacy of this neglect of the environment has, regrettably, been the serious repercussions, both to local ecosystems, public health, and infrastructure, as confirmed by recent studies (Fraser & Lungu, 2007; OAG, 2014; ZEMA, 2024; ZIEM, 2012). The main problems of an environmental nature arising from mining activities are threefold: firstly, the emission of SO₂ and particulate matter (fine and ultrafine) (PM₁₀, PM_{5.0}, PM_{2.5}, PM_{0.1}) from smelters; secondly, the effect of heavy-metals effluents on watercourses; and thirdly, the siltation of local rivers and other aquatic systems. Furthermore, it is important to note that industrial activity is, whilst being so important from an economic viewpoint, a great contributor to air pollution of

such origins. Industries connected with power generation, iron and steel manufacture, and building materials, have a considerable output of noxious gases and particulates, which have been shown to have harmful health effects on adjoining population groups (Marcon et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2023).

Study Area

Zambia is a landlocked country in Southern Africa surrounded by eight countries, namely: the Democratic Republic of Congo on the north, Tanzania on the north-east, Malawi on the east, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Botswana and Namibia on the south and Angola on the west. It lies between 8° and 18° south, and 22° and 34° east. It has an area of 752,614 square kilometres which puts it among the smaller countries of South-Central Africa. It has a population of about 19,610,769 persons (ZamStats, 2022). It is divided into ten administrative provinces, viz: Central, Copperbelt, Eastern, Luapula, Lusaka, Muchinga, Northern, North-Western, Southern and Western (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map Illustrating the Location of the Study Area

The provinces are further subdivided into districts, with Lusaka being the Capital City. It has a subtropical climate characterized by two main seasons: a dry season from May to October and a rainy season from November to April. Rainfall is greatest in the northern provinces (about 1,400 mm annually), while in the southwest it is about 700 mm. October is the hottest month with an average temperature of

about 31.8°C, while July is the coldest month with an average of 8.1°C.

Air Pollution from the Mines

Given the extensive mining history in the Copperbelt, it is important to examine the historical context of air pollution and its management. A major factor is that since the advent of large-scale commercial mining in 1928, smelters were legally protected from liability. This protection was formally granted by the Smoke Damage (Prohibition) Act of 1935, which indemnified the mines from legal responsibility for pollution it caused. Most smelting areas were under British colonial rule when the government designated smelting areas, in Nkana, Luanshya, and Mufulira for example, as Smoke Areas. This was a legal decision which prevented mine operators from any legal responsibility for personal injury or property damage arising from their pollution of the atmosphere.

The policy was a sort of license to pollute, and provided no incentive to reduce emissions. Even with Zambian independence from Britain, and nationalisation of the mines, the Smoke Damage Act had full force of law, indemnifying the ZCCM (the government-managed Zambia Consolidated Copper Mines) from liability for pollution. This Act was not even thought to be unacceptable until 1996 when it was repealed in the wake of the Zambian shift towards multiparty democracy and a somewhat open economy. The privatization of the mines in the late 1990s and early on in the 2000s, saw the principles of the earlier Smoke Damage Act incorporated into the development agreements. New investors received indemnity, and a stability period was created, during the course of which the government could not enforce its pollution penalties against them (OAG, 2014).

Pollution from mining in Zambia caused mostly by SO₂ and PM has been a serious problem since about the 1920s, when mining began on a heavy commercial scale in the Copperbelt. The evidence of pollution on a widespread scale, however, is only beginning to emerge. In 2000 the Air Pollution Information Network for Africa (APINA) made a study to find out what

the levels of air pollution were throughout the country, their study showed that PM10 was the pollutant of highest emission in Zambia. The emission was put at 405.8 kilotonnes per annum (kt/yr), which was 35% of the country's total emissions. The next was SO₂ with 359.6 kt/yr, which was 31% of total emissions. Next came PM2.5, with 252.7 kt per annum emissions; then NH₃ (ammonia) with 75.82 kt/yr, NO_x (nitrogen oxides) with 72.8 kt/yr (ECZ, 2008).

SO₂ is still the most common air pollutant emitted from mining operations. In Zambia the most common source of SO₂ pollution arises from the roasting and refining of copper bearing sulfide ores such as chalcopyrite (CuFeS₂) (Simukanga, 1999). The initial stages of the production of copper typically involves roasting or smelting of the ores to oxidize them in the air during which SO₂ is produced (Mwaanga et al., 2019).

The increase in SO₂ emissions had been historically associated with increases in copper production which was mainly due to the use of old, inefficient smelting technologies (Olli, 2014). In the last two decades however the increasing pressure from international NGO's and financial institutions (Centre for Trade Policy and Development, 2012) and the increased enforcement of air pollution regulations by ZEMA has forced the mining companies to modernize their smelting facilities.

Consequently, four of Zambia's five major mining companies which produce about 80% of the country's copper production have modern smelters with a great increase in the SO₂ capture efficiency. Although this modernization has contributed to a marked reduction in SO₂ emissions, particulate pollution in the form of toxic PM2.5 and PM10 from mining operations continues to present a serious environmental and public health hazard (Mwaanga et al., 2019).

Mining operations (OAG, 2014), contained in an audit report of the Office of the Auditor General, were found to be in violation of statutory limits regarding emissions by a large number of mining companies. The analysis found that the concentrations of SO₂ from four out of five mining companies varied from 358.6

mg/Nm³ to 86 155 mg/Nm³, which was exceptionally above the limits set by ZEMA. Within a 36 month period eight companies declared emissions up to one to thirty times greater than permissible limit, Mopani Copper Mine being the highest recorded, which recorded a statutory level of 155,769 mg/Nm³, or 155% violated the statutory limit (Table 1).

With regard to PM (dust) emissions it was noted that eleven works of five mining companies exceeded the permissible limit from 157.1 mg/Nm³ to 2,679.5 mg/Nm³. In the extreme case of Ndola Lime was observed 5,550 mg/Nm³, which was 111 times more than the permissible 50 mg/Nm³ has been set. The mines were found to have all declared dust emissions above permissible limits for 4 to 28 months in the 36 month period, while Chambishi Copper Smelter failed to take note of dust parameters with regard to Stack No. 1, in violation of ZEMA's licensing regulations and air pollution controls. With regard to arsenic emissions, it was found that the emissions varied from 0.4 mg/Nm³ to 4.7 mg/Nm³, that four of the five mining companies also found abundantly high concentrations of arsenic for 1 to 28 months about seven works. The highest emission occurred at Mopani Copper Mine converter slag-blow stack, which recorded emissions of 38.8 mg/Nm³ or 77.6 times above the permissible limit of 0.5 mg/Nm³. The fact that Ndola Lime as well as Chambishi Copper Smelter sent in

returns without arsenic tests, show the state of compliance of some of the episodes of the works in compliance. In respect to copper emissions, it was found from tables that the acceptable limit was 1.0 mg/Nm³, giving averages of from 2.7 mg/Nm³ to 151.3 mg/Nm³ was found once again Mopani Copper Mine emitting 854.2 mg/Nm³ being 854 times above the accepted limit, and all the limits being found high in terms of limits from 9 to 31 months per assessment period. Ndola Lime and Chambishi Copper Smelter submitted no statistical returns relevant to copper emissions, while other mines submitted a return of statistics for the previous 1 to 3 years on a basis not covering the statutory emission control of the regulations of air quality. Lastly it is noted that there is excessive lead concentrations of the emissions at an average from 0.3 mg/Nm³ to 23.4 mg/Nm³, with three mining companies finding themselves lacking in adherence of the degree of standards for a period of from 5 to 31 months at 6 works. The greatest value once again was noted at Mopani Copper Mine which has emitted 75.9 mg/Nm³, or 379 times above statutory limits of the emissions set of 0.2 mg/Nm³, and besides it was found that Chambishi Copper Smelter had not been able to discern lead from the emissions from Stack No. 1, while Nil of Ndola Lime was noted that the assessments of lead emission controls under all three stacks had been unitable to be put up in conformity with regulatory limitations.

Table 1. Air Pollution - SO₂ from 2009 to 2011

Name of mine and facility	Chambishi Copper Smelter-Chimney 1	Chambishi Copper Smelter-Anode Furnace	Chambishi Copper Smelter-Slag cleaning furnace	Konkola Copper Mine - Nchanga SBU Cobalt recovery furnace	Mopani Copper Mine - Mufulira SBU-Converter slag blow	Mopani Copper Mine - Mufulira SBU-Converter copper blow	Mopani Copper Mine - Mufulira SBU-Acid plant	Mopani Copper Mine - Nkana - Cobalt plant
Units	mg/Nm ³ .	mg/Nm ³ .	mg/Nm ³ .	mg/Nm ³	mg/Nm ³	mg/Nm ³	mg/Nm ³	mg/Nm ³
ZEMA statutory limits	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000
Minimum value	1030.0	0.0	16.2	0.0	15243.5	17149.0	475.4	27152.5

Median value	1182.0	193.6	41.0	148.6	36917.9	40014.0	8303.0	90317.9
Maximum value	1332.0	2550.2	1313.8	1876.9	95272.0	621879.0	14291.0	155769.0
Average value	1182.6	726.7	362.4	358.6	43470.9	62287.7	8311.4	86155.0

Source: (OAG, 2014)

Air pollution from Industries

Industrial development is an essential foundation of the national economy, but the industry is also the largest source of air pollution, of which power plants, iron and steel, building materials, and other industries emit large amounts of pollutants (Wu et al., 2023). Industrial development has been associated with the emissions of large quantities of gaseous and particulate substances with resultant deleterious health effects on the inhabitants of the city (Marcon et al., 2014).

Cement and Lime Production

Cement, a widely used construction material is important to today's civilized world (Aziz et al., 2024; Xi et al., 2016). It is an important construction material for the housing and infrastructural development and a very vital factor in the economic growth of a particular society. The demand for cement is directly proportional the demand for economic growth and a good number of the developing economies in the world are striving for a rapid infrastructural development which brings about an increase in the production of cement (Marcon et al., 2014). Major Cement and lime manufacturing industries in Zambia are: Chilanga Cement Plc, Dangote Cement Plc, Zambezi Portland, Sinoma Cement Co. Ltd., and Limestone Resources Limited, Newcrest Lime Limited, Mpande Limestone Ltd. The global cement industry has been growing due to the increased demand of infrastructures and the rapid development of urbanization, especially in the developing and emerging countries like the sub-Saharan Africa and central and western Asian nations (Chen et al., 2022).

The cement industry has developed progressively in developing and developed countries with an increase in the production of

cement from 2.9 billion tons in 2008 to 4 billion tons in the year 2024 (USGS, 2025). In the year 2024, the production of cement increased by 17.8 percent from a production level of 2768935Mt in the year 2023 to 3262319Mt. This has been attributed to the increased regional demand of the products. The heating of raw materials and the process of grinding makes cement industry an undoubtful source of air pollutant emission (Klimont et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2007) and has adverse effect on the atmospheric environment of the region.

Though required in the infrastructural development, cement production involves the discharge of undesirable emissions such as carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), SO₂, and the PM (Ibrahim et al., 2012). The discharges greatly contribute to the pollution of the ambient air with subsequent danger or detrimental effect on the community health (Cha et al., 2011). The PM is of special environmental concern as they are the biggest percentage of the emission. The major component of the cement dust is hermetical size of 0.05 to 5.0 micrometer (Meo et al., 2013).

Air Pollution from Manganese and Zinc Processing Plants

The processing of manganese ore results in the emission of harmful substances to the atmosphere as a result of obsolete methods, with consequent increased concentration of manganese and other metals into the atmosphere (Avkopashvili et al., 2019). The process of the tapping of metals and slugs, Casting, crushing and screening, results in a considerable emission of PM (Davourie et al., 2017). The processing of Zinc alloy contributes to air pollution through emission of heavy metals in its emissions which comprises of zinc,

lead and cadmium (Sethurajan et al., 2016). Serenje, Mkushi and Kabwe in the Central province has an increased number of manganese processing plants. This is because of the availability of manganese and Zinc ores and the easy availability of electricity in the region. The processes involve the crushing of the ore and the smelting it in the furnace using Coal as a source of fuel. ZEMA has approved several manganese mining processing plants in the province, especially in Serenje district's Pensulo area with some about 13 manganese processing plants within the radius of about 1.6km including others in the outside of this radius.

Figure 2. Annual Manganese Production (Mt) 2019 – 2024

Source: (MoF, 2021, 2024)

In the year 2020, Manganese production increased by 184.3 percent to 132,241 Mt from 46,515 Mt, as illustrated in figure 2. This increase was largely due to the commencement of processing plants in 2021. An increase in the production capacity may be associated with an increase in the emissions levels (MoF, 2021). However, manganese production in 2024 decreased by 21.1 percent to 134,933 Mt from 171,066 Mt produced in 2023. This was attributed to constrained power supply (MoF, 2024). In 2022 ZEMA ordered most the Manganese and Zinc processing plant in Mkushi and Serenje Districts to cease operation and install air abatement systems. Following the directive of the agency a number of facilities have installed the air abatement systems and some of the facilities are even able to monitor their emissions online. However, no research has

been conducted to assess the emissions of air pollutants from these facilities and the ambient air quality around them and the impacts that these emissions may have on human health, plants and the environment.

Air Pollution from Thermal Power Plants

Electricity generation through coal starts with the process of changing heat energy into mechanical energy, that drive turbines and generators to produce electricity. However, these processes produce emissions that have environmental impacts. The air pollutants which cause impacts produced from the coal fired power plants are primarily CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, SO_x, and PM. These emissions may cause increase in global warming and decrease in air quality which have adverse impacts on both man and the environment (Wibawa et al., 2020). Mercury emissions from the coal fired power plants have been recognized as the major industrial source of mercury pollution in China (Hu & Cheng, 2016; Wu et al., 2010). Investigations show that the average mercury content of Chinese coal was 0.22 mg/kg (Wu et al., 2010). But the reality is that most of the power stations in China do not have the precautionary mercury controlling device installed. Thus, the greater part of the mercury contained in the coal is emitted directly into the atmosphere, which has attracted the attention of the whole world (Wu et al., 2010). The mercury emissions from such power plant are influenced by many parameters, such as type and design of the boiler, type of the coal, coal composition, combustion environment, cooling rate, residence time, and air pollution control devices (APCDs), operating practices (boiler load, excess air, etc.) etc. However, the pamphlet relative to mercury emissions from thermal power stations has been limited in China (Wu et al., 2010). Hu and Cheng (2016) reported that power plants, in China, are generally equipped with multi-pollutant control technology, which offer the co benefit of mercury removal, whereas mercury specific control systems have been installed on few plants.

In Zambia, Maamba Energy Limited (MEL) is one the largest Independent Power Producers (IPs) and operates the largest coal mining

concession in Zambia. MEL is operating a 300MW thermal power station at mine-mouth at Maamba. This caters for the large and growing demand for power and contributes 9% to the national installed generation capacity, thereby adding diversity in sources of supply of power, contributing to the security of supply and economic development of the country, whilst ensuring sustainable community development. MEL uses eco-friendly and modern mining equipment and processes while at the same time the power plant uses modern technology to minimize environmental impacts in compliance with world bank and ZEMA standards (MEL, 2023). In Zambia today there is the energy crisis presently faced and this means that thermal power stations are in the course of getting commissioned in the country, which will cause the increase in emissions levels.

Figure 3. Emissions from Boiler 1
Source: (MCL, 2025)

Figure 4. Emissions from boiler 2
Source: (MCL, 2025)

Figure 3 and 4, showing the emissions levels from the coal fired power plant in Zambia in the Southern Province. All the pollutants are well within the ZEMA emissions standard, which have been set in the Environmental Management Licensing Regulation No 12 of 2013 except of course in regard to the dust emissions which were slightly above the limits. It is apparent that this was due to the starting up of the power plant and stabilization after shut down (MCL, 2025).

Steel and Iron Manufacturing and Processing Industries

The iron and steel industry are one of the main sources of emissions of the pollutant PM because of its great energy and pollution intensity. The PM from the emission of the iron and steel industry contains dangerous products, such as heavy metals and noxious elements, which are dangerous for the environment as well as the human beings (Jia et al., 2018). Integrated iron and steel works are made up of several plants involving closely interrelated generation units, such as sintering plants, coking plant, ironmaking plants, steelmaking plants, rolling plants and other logistical plants or workshops (X.-j. Liu et al., 2018). Each of these plants emits both stack and fugitively emitted particulate matter (FPM). PM source apportionment is a good tool to establish information about the emission sources and the extent of which they contribute to the ambient pollution levels (Almeida et al., 2020). Therefore, it is of great importance to determine the physical and chemical information of that emitted PM, which originates from the same iron and steel works (Ogundele et al., 2016). There have been made a lot of investigations in order to find the emission factors from sources in the iron and steel industry. Tang et al. (2020) have investigated the extent of contribution of the PM emissions of the iron and steel industry in China in relation to the ambient air quality at the national scale, and it was concluded that sintering was the biggest contributor, giving 45.81% and 47.99% of the PM10 and PM2.5 emissions respectively. PM10 consists of inhalable PM, i.e. particles with aerodynamic diameter below 10 µm, and PM2.5

fine PM, i.e. particles with aerodynamic diameter on a lower order than $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (Sun et al., 2020).

Amodio et al. (2013) have made monitoring and assessment of the FPM emission influence from a residential area nearby to the largest European steel plant on ambient level concentrations. Khare and Baruah (2011) have reported for refractorily operated coking plants that the PM_{2.5} emission factors are between 0.7 and 3 kg/t, and the totals of the emissions ranges from 72 to 306 tons per year. Sun et al. (2019) has made measurements for 22 stack emission sources from a steel works, and from these measurements it was concluded that coke pusher and guide car have contributed most to the extent of PM concentration of emission, to 38.12 mg/m³, and sintering machine and bulk materials room, 36.00 and 35.23 mg/m³, respectively. Burners for thermal power produce the lowest grade of PM, 6.7 mg/m³.

In Zambia has iron- and steel scrap recycling been a double advantage concerning its contribution to that it represents in the occasion of secondary steel- foundry. The fact that it is a source of raw materials or a way of managing waste of completing materials which otherwise would be emissions of harmful hazy things in the various conveying forms of environmental hazards. The leading industries of Zambia in this direction this sector includes: MMI Steel Zambia Limited, Chisteel Zambia Limited, Heroes Foundry and Engineering, Good time steel, Scaw limited, SKS Steel Zambia Limited, Universal Mining & Chemical Industries Limited, Fine steel Manufacturing. Production system is a recycling production system. It consists of melting the scrap metals at very high temperatures, between 1,200 and 1,700 °C. A significant source of PM in the production process is given by the ingredient's unit.

The growing demand for iron rods, coupled with the availability of scrap metals has accelerated the growth of secondary iron and steel smelters in Zambia. This rapid growth has not been supported with stringent regulations that are requisite for environmental and personnel protection. Some of the steel and iron recycling industries have lack installed air pollution control systems on their production processes as

required. The emissions that are produced, which include a variety of air pollutants that are associated with the iron smelter production processes, has been a source of great concern (Brook et al., 2004; Brunekreef & Forsberg, 2005; Katsouyanni, 2005). Each production step involved in the steel making, using Electric Arc Furnace (EAF), results in the emission of the pollutants (Margolis et al., 1999). The PM_{2.5} and PM_{2.5-10} fractions of the PM (Rickun, 1993) produced are the principle pollutants of concern, which are produced at virtually every stage of the production process. With the multitude of pollutants resultant from the production process, there is need to quantify the emissions sources and describe their potential impact on the ambient air concentrations of the pollutants and the human health effects (Brook et al., 2004; Brunekreef & Forsberg, 2005; Katsouyanni, 2005). Organic carbon (OC), black carbon (BC), heavy and trace metals are among the PM species emitted from iron and steel production processes, and this class of compounds makes up a major, sometimes dominating, fraction of atmospheric PM. BC is the main light-absorbing species in the atmosphere, which plays an important role in the aerosol climatic and visibility degradation (Bond et al., 2013; Jacobson, 2001; Malm et al., 2000; Tegen et al., 1997). BC has been found to be also a large contributor to finer particulate mass (Begum et al., 2011; Chow et al., 1996; Kirchstetter et al., 1999). Heavy metals, such as As, Cd and Cr, are toxic, even in trace amounts. This has been reported to be constituents of PM associated with iron and steel production (Cohen et al., 2004).

Air Pollution from Other Industrial Sources

Block and Brick Making Factories

Blocks and bricks are important construction materials used for housing and infrastructure development, and key to any economic growth of a given society just as cement is. There has been an increase in the number of block and brick manufacturing industries in Zambia. This is due to the increasing demand of concrete products such as solid concrete blocks, hollow concrete blocks, pavers, curb stones, concrete

blocks, lintal blocks and burnt clay bricks that are used for construction. Thus, the demand for blocks and bricks is proportional to that of cement, and economic growth of the country. However, the main problem with this type of industry is that of dust, that is PM 10 and PM 2.5 mainly from the stock piled quarry dust and the actual block making processes. Some of these factories are situated in residential areas.

The raw materials that are used in the production of blocks and bricks include clay, dense and light aggregate, calcium silicate, natural stones and cement. The blocks and bricks have approximately 30 percent crystalline silicate, while concrete and cement mortar contain between 25 and 70% % (Mwanaumo et al., 2023). Sand and stone (quartzite) have got more than 70%. Health hazards like silicosis, bronchitis chronic and callousness, skin diseases and respiratory, fatigue, headaches, hearing problems and many others are among the diseases which are increasing in the employees of this industry (Saha et al., 2020).

For instance, in study which was carried by % Mwanaumo et al. (2023) on the Identification of Operational Safety Risks in Block and Brick Production Facilities in Zambia. It was observed that the prevalence of safety risks were frequent complaints by workers such as cough (46.2%), phlegm (41.1%), wheezing (36.9%), and sneezing (45.5%), due to dust in the factories while dermatives (60.2%) due to non-utilization of PPEs.

In Zambia, brick making factories mostly utilize the traditional methods, in some cases firewood, charcoal and coal are utilized as fuel. In Bangladesh technologies used for the brick production such as clamps, high draught kilns and bull's trench kilns consumes large quantities of fuel such as coal, fire wood and any other biomass (Begum et al., 2010). The process results in the emission of air pollutions into the atmosphere which may impact human health and the environment. The main pollutions which are emitted from the brickfields are PM some hazardous gases like CO₂, CO, NO_x, NO and SO₂. The PM concentration is shown to be lower but it has a long term tremendous effect on global environment as well as on human health.

The PM consists of dust, smoke, fumes and fly ash (Darain et al., 2013; Raza & Ali, 2021; Skinder et al., 2014). Most of these brick making factories has no air pollution control devices. But not research has been carried to see the air quality from the pollution of these factories and area surrounding these factories. And also assess the effect which may be associated with these air pollutions on human health, trees and the environment.

Other Manufacturing Industries

The combustion of coal, which has a complicated chemical composition (Sheta et al., 2019), leads to the release of diverse impurities such as soot, or PM, SO₂, NO_x, or organics (Pudasainee et al., 2010; Shi et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2015; Yan et al., 2016). Consequently, the major contributors to air pollution from industrial processes are coal fired boilers. Thus, in Chinese industrial processes, the burning of coal by boilers contributes hugely to mercury emissions (Hu & Cheng, 2016). Fine PM (i.e. aerodynamic diameter $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, PM_{2.5}) emanating from combustion processes might concentrate toxic heavy metals, organics, and other hazardous materials, due to their higher specific surface area and high reactivity (Anderson et al., 2002; Choi et al., 2012). The large amounts of PM_{2.5} produced can also appreciate the frequency of hazy weather, and after being inhaled, may lead to respiratory diseases, asthma included (Ding & Zhou, 2014; Yao et al., 2009). One of the major suppliers of PM is industrial combustion process (Cano et al., 2017). Coal fired industrial boilers are responsible for about 80 percent of the entire capacity of industrial dynamic boilers, and produce more: PM than coal-fired power generation (Dong et al., 2018; Xue et al., 2016).

Lusaka, Ndola and Kabwe are cities in Zambia with a number of industries which operates on coal and fuel fired boilers. Among these industries are; heating supply, food manufacturing and feedstock manufacturing, chemical, fertilizer, pharmaceuticals, papermaking were the major industries contributing to the emissions. Some of these industrial boilers are equipped with the air abatement systems such as wet scrubbers or

multi-cyclones. While, most of them have only basic or no flue gas cleaning or air pollution control system in place. While the majority of these industries are situated within established industrial zones, some are found in newly developed residential areas that local authorities have reclassified for mixed land use. These are some of the facilities that sometimes brings about complaints of air pollution to the communities near these facilities. Emissions from these facilities has the potentials of causing impacts on human health and the environment.

Air Pollution from Waste Disposal

Other sources of air pollution include incineration and the open burning of healthcare and other waste. Globally, incineration and sanitary landfilling are the most common practices for medical waste disposal (Hong et al., 2018), but more than 90% of this waste is disposed of in open dumps or is burned in uncontrolled conditions producing by-products such as dioxins and heavy metals due to the lack of emission-control technologies (F. Liu et al., 2018). Many of the aspects surrounding why the waste is generated in the first place, and putting stress on the disposal sites, they include; industrial growth, population increase (expanding waste), the growth of packaging material from consumer products, and the country's low recycling rates, limiting many local authorities (LAs) effectively managing waste. In the past, many of the local authorities had no designated place of disposal; this has changed somewhat, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Percentage of LAs that have Established Designated Waste Disposal Areas

Source: (ZEMA, 2017)

Despite the increase in the number of designated disposal sites, there has been low waste collection rates at 6.3 percent (14.4 percent urban and 0.2 percent rural) resulting in indiscriminate disposal of waste in the country (ZEMA, 2017). Figure 6 shows waste collection rates per province for 2006, 2010 and 2015.

Figure 6. Waste Collection Rates per Province

Source: (ZEMA, 2017).

Most of the domestic waste end in illegal dump sites, and often burnt contributing to air pollution. Most LAs have not been able to provide adequate waste management services. The poor attitude by the general public combined by lack of alternatives, has contributed to inappropriate waste disposal and the increase in illegal disposal sites. The inadequate management of waste contributes to GHGs emissions particularly methane from landfills and CO₂ from open air burning respectively (ZEMA, 2017).

Figure 7. Uchi Disposal Site in Kitwe

Source: (ZEMA, 2017)

Some wastes are being incinerated at a low temperature resulting into incomplete combustion. and emissions of toxic gases such as dioxins and furans which are Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) (ZEMA, 2017). This may subsequently result in severe health ailments among people that may be exposed to them. Nevertheless, incinerators continue to be the preferred means of disposal of medical waste in most countries of transitional economy. In former days, in Zambia most of the waste were being burnt in incinerators made of old bricks, some of them using fire wood as the fuel, and without any air pollution control systems. These were mostly found in mani hospitals and schools for burning both the medical waste and some of the solid wastes. However, there is a small but gradual improvement, especially in the case of mini hospitals and district hospitals, where piloted brick incinerators have been replaced with those fuel fired. However, very little or no research has been done to find out the emission levels from these incinerators and old brick incinerators. And what effects would these emissions have on human beings, plants and the environment. There are a number of proposals made to remedy the environmental paper with regard to the indiscriminate disposal of waste. For instance, time wide to convert waste to energy (conversion of human and animal excreta, and other organic waste into biogas), briquetting and pelletisation of wastes such as

sawdust, newspapers and agriculture waste (rice husks, groundnut husks, maize cobs) (ZEMA, 2017).

Ambient Air Quality Monitoring

Ambient air quality information is crucial for protecting public health, preserving the environment, and promoting sustainable economic development. Such data are of key importance for improving management and understanding whether environmental laws are being effectively complied with. More generally, it influences activities aimed at preventing the further deterioration of air quality. ZEMA conducted assessment of Ndola and Lusaka air quality from data (2020-2024) of an Ambient Air Sampling Machine commissioned in Zambia. Authors monitored concentrations for SO₂, ozone (O₃), nitrogen oxides (NO, NO₂, NO_x), CO, CO₂ and PM2.5 and PM10 to determine whether measurements are within regulatory limits. Table 2 shows the Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Data in Lusaka and Ndola district. The table below shows that all measured pollutant concentrations fell within ZEMA's regulatory limits. These relatively low levels are likely influenced by the nature of activities in the areas where sampling was conducted.

Table 2. Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Data for Lusaka and Ndola

Parameter	Location	Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Average Value	Limit
SO ₂ (µg/m ³)	Lusaka	0.00786	0.22798	0.05539	500
	Ndola	0.00786	0.26729	0.03231	500
O ₃ (µg/m ³)	Lusaka	-0.03337	0.12564	0.03018	125
	Ndola	0.00393	0.12172	0.03853	125
NO (µg/m ³)	Lusaka	0.00123	0.03436	0.00442	400
	Ndola	0.00123	0.03928	0.0073	400
NO ₂ (µg/m ³)	Lusaka	-0.00188	0.04328	0.00769	400
	Ndola	0.00376	0.05833	0.01723	400
NO _x (µg/m ³)	Lusaka	-0.00188	0.0828	0.01266	-
	Ndola	0.00565	0.09974	0.02845	-
CO (mg/m ³)	Lusaka	0.00786	0.22798	0.05539	10
	Ndola	0.00786	0.26729	0.03228	10
CO ₂ (µg/m ³)	Lusaka	339.004	403.589	362.924	-
	Ndola	166.164	562.049	337.053	-

Source: (ZEMA, 2024)

In both Lusaka and Ndola, the monitoring points were situated in zones dominated by commercial, residential, and institutional land uses, which generally produce lower emissions. Monitoring could not be performed in major emission hotspots, such as agricultural and industrial areas, due to the malfunctioning of supplementary equipment, including the portable air monitoring device. This equipment failure also reduced the number of sampling locations, resulting in data that were biased toward areas with minimal pollutant levels.

Data reported by ZEMA (2017) show that dust pollution was a major concern in both Lusaka and Ndola during 2009 and 2010. Measurements from both monitoring locations exceeded national and international air quality standards, as illustrated in Figures 8 and 9.

Figure 8. Dust in Ambient Air Monitored in Lusaka in 2010
Source: (ZEMA, 2017)

Figure 9. Dust in Ambient Air Monitored in Ndola in 2009 and 2010
Source: (ZEMA, 2017)

Impacts of Air Pollution on Human Health

Almost the entire population of the planet (99%) are exposed to levels of air pollution that put them at increased risk of heart disease, stroke, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, cancer and pneumonia. 6.7 million deaths worldwide are thought to have resulted from exposure to ambient and household air pollution in 2019 (WHO, 2025a). Pollutants of major public health concern include PM, CO, O₃, NO_x and SO₂ (WHO, 2025a). Several studies have shown that air pollution has severe impact on human health (Bernstein et al., 2004; Tao et al., 2003).

According to WHO (2025b), the burden of air pollution health impact in Zambia in 2019 was staggering, at an estimated 153262 attributable death. The impact is overwhelmingly cardiorespiratory, with Acute Lower Respiratory Infections in children being the killer, at roughly 65% of the burden. Air pollution also drives noncommunicable diseases, with Stroke and Ischaemic Heart Disease responsible in combination for almost a third of attributable mortality, and significant delivery also coming from the chronic lung diseases and Lung Cancer. The uncertainty intervals underline a need for more local data but nonetheless tell a clear story of air pollution as a pressing public health emergency in need of a co-ordinated policy response across multiple sectors. Kapungwe et al. (2001) report that world-wide data show that brief exposure to concentrations above 1000 µg/m³ has been fatal, and such exposures have often been encountered in Zambian mining towns such as Mufulira and Kitwe.

The Occupational Health and Safety Institute of Zambia (OHSIZ), a statutory body under the Ministry of Health, is tasked with medical surveillance and health research for miners, with a special focus on silicosis and related lung diseases. Silicosis is a fatal and irreversible lung scarring caused by prolonged inhalation of silica dust, as defined by (Greenberg et al., 2007). The disease has a long latency period and manifests in acute, accelerated, or chronic forms following

substantial occupational exposure (Mwaanga et al., 2019).

Paul (1961) conducted the first descriptive epidemiological study of silicosis in Zambian copper miners while working with OHSIZ, and reported a low prevalence of lower than 0.5%. However, his work did not contain age stratified data, which was by the early 1970's was acknowledged by OHSI researchers, who age stratified their work and provided a greater prevalence - of around 5% - in miners who were older, and still working (Hayumbu, 2012).

Sitembo (2012) performed a retrospective review of 476 randomly selected medical records of former Zambian copper mineworkers examined at OHSIZ between 1 January 2004 and 31 December 2008. The prevalence of silicosis was found to be 8.8%. Subjects diagnosed with this disease had a median of 26 years of mining service compared with 21 years for those not affected.

While not endemic to mining populations, this disease often poses a significant health burden in the Zambian population and has also been ascribed to exposure to respirable silica dust in underground mines. In mineworkers with silicosis, silica-related tuberculosis (TB) proved to be particularly problematic. In their review of medical records from 2,114 Zambian miners, covering the years 1945–2002, Mulenga et al. (2005) while not concentrating specifically on occupational lung disease per se, found that 22.7% of the miners had silicosis, 65.4% TB, while 11.9% suffered from silico-tuberculosis. On computing the epidemiology of TB using both a national TB register and the OHSIZ

database (a mine health and safety database), the same authors documented that, the weighted average incidence of bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB (PTB), between 1994 and 2014, was 658 cases per 100000 people in the Zambian mines (Chanda-Kapata et al., 2016). The Copperbelt Province (where most of the country's mines are located) had a notification rate of TB of 415 per 100000 in 2013, ten times higher than the national rate of less than 40 per 100000.

Humans may also be inadvertently exposed to airborne pollutant emissions from mining and ore-processing activities via the food chain (Mwaanga et al., 2019). Konečný et al. (2014) rather alarming reported significant chemical contamination of cassava leaves, the second most important staple crop in Zambia grown close to Copperbelt smelters. The leaves closest to the point of smelting were coated with fine dust containing potentially harmful concentrations of heavy metals. This contamination was demonstrated by comparing the level of metals in washed and unwashed cassava leaves (Table 3). The highest acceptable weekly intake based on guidelines from the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (Udiba et al., 2019), indicated that consuming uncooked cassava leaves and tubers could present a moderate health risk due to exposure to metals. Because surfaces of cassava leaves in polluted areas of the Copperbelt were heavily contaminated with metalliferous dust, preparing a dish using such cassava leaves that had not been adequately washed may still lead to the ascertainable ingestion of hazardous levels of copper, lead, and arsenic.

Table 3. Concentrations (mg kg⁻¹) of Metals Measured

Element	Unwashed leaves MED ± MAD	Washed leaves MED ± MAD	% of element removed
As	0.08 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	12.0
Co	1.30 ± 0.05	0.60 ± 0.03	53.8
Cu	35.95 ± 5.74	20.12 ± 1.12	44.0
Fe	800.20 ± 51.0	183.00 ± 0.0	77.1
Pb	0.71 ± 0.11	0.61 ± 0.11	14.3
Zn	345.20 ± 6.16	316.27 ± 4.43	8.4

Note: Concentrations (mg kg⁻¹) of Metals Measured in both unwashed and thoroughly washed cassava leaves from a contaminated site in the Copperbelt region, along with the percentage of each metal removed through washing (expressed as a proportion of the levels found in unwashed leaves). MED = median value, MAD = median absolute deviation, based on five samples.

Source: (Kříbek et al., 2014)

The emissions from the cement and lime industries are largely responsible for the contamination of the surrounding air resulting in subsequent hazards or ill effects on the health of the community (Cha et al., 2011). The PM is of special environmental concern as they constitute the largest percentage of the emission. The major constituent of the cement dust is hermetical size of 0.05 to 5.0 microone (Meo et al., 2013). These particles when breathed into the lungs will penetrate into the areas of gas exchange thereby placing the workers and the residents of the communities to risk of respiratory diseases (Bertoldi et al., 2012; Cha et al., 2011). The individuals at risk are those who live in the cities, where those activities that bring about air pollution are sited; especially the ones who live near the factories such as cement factories, live within the radius of fallout or dispersion and workers in these plants (Mwaiselage et al., 2004).

Some epidemiological studies have reported impairment of the lung health in the individuals who are exposed to cement dust in the communities who are residing near cement factories. The commonest reported respiratory symptoms include cough, wheeze, dyspnea, nasal catarrh, sneezing, and phlegm (Al-Neaimi et al., 2001; Ginns & Gatrell, 1996; Kakooei et al., 2012). Also, pulmonary function indices measured as forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1), forced vital capacity (FVC), FEV1/FVC ratio, and peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) have also been shown to be reduced (Al-Neaimi et al., 2001; Mwaiselage et al., 2004). But some studies have shown that there are no statistically significant relationship on the exposure of cement dust and respiratory ill health (Nordby et al., 2011; Siziya, 2008). Therefore, due to the inconsistent results, there has been no concordance, on the relationship between the exposure of cement dust and respiratory ill health.

A study done by (Siziya, 2008) at one of the limestone factory in Zambia on 70 workers those from the production department who were highly exposed, 40 who were from engineering department and medium exposed

and 30 workers who were lowly exposed were selected from the administration. The result of the lungs health of the workers showed a high prevalence of respiratory illness most in the production staff. The report concluded that, results showed that exposure to dust of limestone is associated with prevalent increase in the prevalence of respiratory symptoms. Therefore, there is need to put the proper use of the personal protective equipment until new technology is established. For instances studies by Nkhama et al. (2015) shows that, that the prevalence of pulmonary symptoms was higher in the residents of an area very near compared.

Another key lesson from Zambia's mining legacy is that human exposure to toxic substances can persist for decades after mining activities have ceased. This is clearly illustrated in Kabwe district, where open-pit lead–zinc mining operated from 1902 until its closure in 1994. In addition to lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn), cadmium (Cd) was also generated as a by-product of zinc ore processing (Mwaanga et al., 2019). Yabe et al. (2018) assessed Pb and Cd levels in the blood, feces, and urine of children from three townships located near the abandoned mine. They reported extremely high faecal Pb concentrations (up to 2252 mg/kg dry weight) and urine Pb levels (up to 2914 mg/L). Elevated Cd levels were also detected, with blood Cd reaching 7.7 mg/L, faecal concentrations up to 4.49 mg/kg (dry weight), and urine Cd levels up to 18.1 mg/L. An earlier study by the same authors found that all 246 sampled children showed signs of lead poisoning, with blood lead levels (BLLs) above the CDC's 5 µg/dL threshold of concern (Betts, 2012). The mean BLL was 59.4 µg/dL, ranging from 5.4 to 427.8 µg/dL. Children residing closest to the mine dumps and downwind of the site exhibited the highest metal burdens, indicating that contaminated dust was the primary exposure pathway. The study characterized the Pb and Cd levels observed in children as alarming and recommended urgent medical intervention. Investigations by (CEJ, 2023) revealed that a permanent brain-damaging health condition with symptoms similar to Parkinson's disease had hit about 28 workers at one of the

manganese processing company in Serenje. Ministry of Health records indicated that 28 people had shown symptoms of loss of balance, tremors, impaired speech, uncomfortable drooling or dropping saliva from the mouth and decreased movements (NAZ, 2025). And that blood samples taken by Occupational Health and Safety Institute - OHSI from 281 employees, results revealed that 271, which was 96.4% of the employees, had blood levels of manganese above the normal level. The results showed in the ranges of 0.116 to 0.623 parts per million. The average was 0.244 parts per million. The standard range is from 0.005 ppm up to 0.02 ppm. The strange disease that was observed was manganism or manganese poisoning. The disease resulted from repeated occupational exposure to manganese. The manganism or manganese poisoning is a toxic condition resulting from chronic exposure to manganese. The company had changed the type of manganese ore feed on. The ore introduced was a fine manganese concentrate sourced from Kabwe District. It is later converted into pellets bound by 5 per cent cement. This resulted in high dust fumes in the process of smelting at the plant. It potentially increased the risk of workers to over exposure to manganese (NAZ, 2025).

Conclusion

This review has shown that mining, industrial activities and poor waste management are significant, interlinked sources of air pollution in Zambia. The historic copper mining on the Copperbelt and its one hundred-plus years of high emission of SO₂ and PM have set the tone for environmental and public health challenges that manifest even with the intervention of institutional upgrading and the introduction of regulations. The post-colonial proliferation of other industries (such as cement and lime production, manganese and zinc treatment, manufacturing of steel, thermal power generation) may have diversified the national economy but has also led to the public facing a wider array of airborne contaminants.

The analysis points out that while Zambia has a robust legal framework in its Environmental Management Act and supporting regulations, there is a deficit in enforcement and monitoring

of compliance. Mining and other major industrial sectors, specifically in major mining centres, have repeatedly exceeded statutory emissions, often by wide margins. Disease burden, with ambient and household air pollution accounting for some 153,262 deaths (mostly from cardiorespiratory diseases) were recorded in 2019. The impacts on the ecosystem, including disruption of food chains due to bioaccumulation of toxic metals, soil and vegetation degradation and destruction, and acid rain plus soiling leading to infrastructure deterioration, cannot be ignored either. Examples in Kabwe where lead poisoning ensued and the more recent case of manganism in nearby Serenje illustrate how irreversible loss of lives and/or sources of livelihood are ensured by continued exposure to industrial pollutants that are not addressed neither by the miners nor the government.

The more recent and growing encroachment of urban and medical waste, and how low the collection rate really is, only compounds the air quality chaos, with dumps emitting POPs and greenhouse gases! In short, Zambia has the legal mechanisms to address air pollution, but it needs to approach it in a multi-sectoral manner if it is to avert and reverse the serious impacts. Suggestions include:

- i. Strengthened monitoring, enforcement, and assistance to ensure full compliance by the industrial sector;
- ii. More funding in modern, cleaner technologies from polluting industries with supporting government incentives for local investments;
- iii. Enhanced ambient air quality monitoring networks especially in high emitting zones;
- iv. More funding of public health and epidemiological studies, and prioritisation of public health interventions tailored towards these issues;
- v. Transition from open burning and flying dump sites to a more controlled waste management system overall.

A multi-faceted solution is not just for air quality-promoting policy, but also for public health and the social good, and is important for achieving Zambia's commitment to a greener economy at a minimum.

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